

A NOTE ON THE LIMITS OF SUPERSATURATION AND
THE HEAT OF SOLUTION

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In a series of papers published by the author (this *Journal* 1943, 20, *et seq.*), it has been shown that if $T_s - T$ denotes the degree of supersaturation; λ , the heat of solution of the solute in question; σ , the interfacial tension between the solute and its solution and V_m , the molar volume of the solute, then, in general, $(T_s - T) \lambda$ varies as σV_m . In cases where σV_m values are approximately equal, $(T_s - T) \lambda$ values are also approximately the same. The experimental evidence is summarised in Table I.

TABLE I

Substance.	λ .	$T_s - T$.	$(T_s - T) \lambda$.	Substance.	λ .	$T_s - T$.	$(T_s - T) \lambda$.
KCl	4046	19.6	78897	NaClO ₃	5600	12.0	67200
KBr	5080	16.3	80804	NaCl	1220	51.0	62220
KI	5110	15.5	79205	NH ₄ Cl*	3880	20.0	77600
KBrO ₃	9760	8.8	84788	(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ *	2370	24.0	56880
KIO ₃	6780	13.5	92490	NH ₄ NO ₃	6320	10.3	65016
KClO ₃	9950	6.6	65670	HgCl ₂	3300	25.0	82500
KNO ₃	8800	13.0	114400 (?)	CuSO ₄ **	2750	36.7	80925
KClO ₄	12100	6.3	76230	NaClO ₄ **	3600	20.0	72000
KCNS	6100	13.0	79300	NH ₄ ClO ₄ **	6360	12.0	76320
NaNO ₃	5030	13.0	65399	Ba(ClO ₄) ₂ **	9400	9.0	84600

*Not very regular.

**Unpublished yet.

From Table I it is clear that $(T_s - T) \lambda$ is very approximately a constant and the mean value lies in the neighbourhood of 80,000 cal.

The constancy of the expression $(T_s - T) \lambda$ denotes that a solute possessing a higher heat of solution in water has a greater tendency for recrystallisation from aqueous supersaturated solution and *vice versa*. An attempt has been made to explain this result in this communication.

Let us imagine that a solute dissolves in vacuum, then the heat of solution, say λ_v , under these circumstances, will be equal to the lattice energy of the solute in question (cf. Fajans, *Ber. physikal. Ges.*, 1919, 21, 549; Butler, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1924, 113, 283). We can now substitute hypothetical solvent 'vacuum' with a real solvent, say water. The heat of the solution, say λ_w , which will now be required for dissolution of the solute, instead of λ_v , should, from an analogy with solution in vacuum, correspond to the lattice energy of the solute when it is kept in contact with the solvent water. The heat of solution, like lattice energy, is a kind of potential energy and part of this latent heat energy, under appropriate conditions, can be converted into mechanical work. One of the possible, and perhaps most probable way, is when the solute crystallises out from

its supersaturated solution. When a nucleus of radius r is formed from a supersaturated solution, the work done is $2M\sigma/\rho r$, M being the molecular weight and ρ , the density of the solute in the solid state. If we consider only such solutes for which $\sigma M/\rho$ or σV_m values are approximately equal, then during the formation of a particle of radius r^* , the same amount of work will be done in all the cases. Hence, those cases in which the crystal (or lattice) forming units have absorbed a higher heat of solution and thus possess a higher potential energy, will have a greater tendency for performing the work $2V_m/r$ i. e. a greater tendency for crystallisation, and therefore a solute possessing a higher heat of solution will, in general, crystallise out with greater ease and *vice versa*.

The above considerations imply that the heat of solution should be inversely proportional to the limit of supersaturation as measured by $T_s - T$. In other words, $(T_s - T)\lambda$ should be a constant and this is, in fact, the experimental result as given in Table I. Thus we see that it is possible to explain the result $(T_s - T)\lambda = \text{a constant}$, if the heat of solution is considered as the lattice energy of the solute when it is kept in contact with the solution.

* The radius of the nucleus formed at first T and various T_s in these substances lies in the neighbourhood of 1×10^{-6} cm. (this *Journal*, 1944, 21, 105; cf. also Davis, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 38, 1173; and Harbury, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1946, 80, 190).

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